

A prospective randomized-controlled trial study comparing Segmental spinal anesthesia and general anesthesia in modified radical mastectomy (MRM) surgeries.

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Abstract —

TITLE: A prospective randomized-controlled trial study comparing Segmental spinal anesthesia and general anesthesia in modified radical mastectomy (MRM) surgeries.

AIM & OBJECTIVE: MRM is associated with moderate-to-severe postoperative pain, nausea, and vomiting. The study aims to assess the safety, efficacy, perioperative outcomes, and patient satisfaction associated with these two anesthetic techniques. The choice of anesthesia whether segmental spinal anesthesia (SSA) or general anesthesia (GA) can significantly impact patient outcomes.

MATERIAL & METHODS: 30 patients were enrolled in this comparative study with inclusion criteria of ASA physical status I-II, primary breast cancer scheduled for unilateral mastectomy with axillary dissection. They were randomly divided into two. The segmental spinal anesthesia

Group (SSA) (n = 15) underwent segmental thoracic spinal anesthesia with Isobaric Inj. Levobupivacaine and Inj. fentanyl at T5-T6 interspace, while other group (n = 15) underwent general anesthesia (GA). Intraoperative hemodynamic, postoperative complications, postoperative pain and analgesic consumption, postoperative adverse effects, and patient satisfaction with the anesthetic techniques were recorded.

RESULTS: Results were calculated in form percentage, mean, standard deviation. Intraoperative hypertension (26.6%) was more frequent in group GA, while hypotension (13%) and bradycardia (20%) were more frequent in SSA group. Postoperative nausea (40%) and vomiting (46.6%)

were more frequent in GA group. Postoperative discharge time from Postoperative room was shorter in SSA group (121 ± 8.2 min) than in GA group (211.3 ± 24.3 min). The quality of postoperative analgesia and analgesic consumption was better in SSA group. Patient & surgeon satisfaction was better in SSA group.

CONCLUSIONS: SSA technique provides better satisfaction with excellent postoperative analgesia and fewer complications in patients undergoing breast cancer surgery compared to GA and can be considered as a sole anesthetic technique in breast cancer surgery.

Keywords: General anesthesia, Segmental spinal anesthesia, Ropivacaine, Dexmedetomidine, Fentanyl.

I. INTRODUCTION

The incidence of breast cancer, as well as the need for surgical treatment, has increased probably due to prevention campaigns and modern diagnostic tools. Nowadays, surgical intervention is more conservative, but in most cases, partial or total mastectomy associated with axillary exploration to remove lymph nodes for staging or immune-chemical testing is still necessary. [1] In India, breast cancer is the most common cancer among women, with a higher incidence in urban areas than in rural areas. With advances in imaging techniques, more cases of carcinoma breast are being diagnosed at an early stage. Approximately, 40–60% of breast surgery patients endure severe acute postoperative pain, with over 10% of patients experiencing severe pain for 6–12 months (post mastectomy pain syndrome). Intraoperative and post-operative pain is usually managed by opioids but are usually linked with adverse effects including prolonged sedation, respiratory depression, and post-operative nausea and vomiting (PONV) [2,3]. The drawbacks of GA include, but not limited to, inadequate pain control due to a lack of residual analgesia, high incidence of nausea and vomiting, and increasing the length of hospitalization [4] Thoracic segmental spinal anesthesia has been described in several groups of patients, for example, laparoscopic cholecystectomy, abdominal cancer, breast cancer surgeries, and other procedures [5] Thoracic segmental spinal anesthesia in combination with same sided erector spinae plane block (ESPB) for post-operative analgesia is a novel anesthetic technique which is being used for various surgeries including breast cancer surgeries such as modified radical mastectomy [6]. In patients, where there is increased risk of complications of GA such as patients with hemodynamic instability, thoracic segmental spinal anesthesia also has an added advantage of improved quality of post-operative analgesia, lower incidence of nausea and vomiting, and shorter recovery time. However, there is a minimal risk of hypotension or bradycardia as is common with any spinal anesthesia [7] The erector spinae block provides the advantage of an excellent analgesia by covering both the visceral and somatic pain It offers

advantage over the paravertebral block by eliminating the disadvantage of multiple pricks for every dermatome in a patient of breast cancer.

II. METHOD

After getting approval from the ethical committee, a prospective, randomized, double blind controlled trial was conducted in a period of 6 months. (April 2023- September 2023). Population under study was patients posted for modified radical mastectomy with ASA grade I to ASA grade III. Simple random sampling done by computer generated numbers.

Inclusion criteria:

1. Patients undergoing modified radical mastectomy with axillary dissection
2. Age between 18 and 60 years
3. ASA Grade I to III.

Exclusion criteria:

1. Patients refused thoracic spinal anesthesia
2. Thrombocytopenia or coagulopathy
3. Local site infections
4. Allergic to local anesthetics
5. Patients in whom conversion to GA was required.

All patients pre anesthetic checkup done with informed consent about thoracic spinal anesthesia along with ESPB (Erector spinae plane block) and general anesthesia in detail. 30 Patients were randomly divided into 2 groups Group SSA (n=15) & group GA (n=15). Group SSA was given thoracic segmental anesthesia along with erector spinae plane block (ESPB) and group GA was given general anesthesia. Standard American Society of Anesthesiologists (ASA) monitors were attached – ECG, ETCO₂, NIBP, SPO₂, and IV access on the opposite arm was taken.

ESPB was given at T5 level using 15 mL 0.5% Ropivacaine (plain isobaric) on the side to be operated (using 23 g spinal needle). Thoracic spinal anesthesia was then given in the same position (sitting/lateral) by median or paramedian technique using 26 g spinal needle at T5–T6 level with Inj. Ropivacaine 0.5% (isobaric) 1.2–1.3 mL + 5 ug dexmedetomidine. General Anesthesia was induced with inj. propofol (1.5-2.5 mg/kg), inj. fentanyl (2 µg/kg), and inj. vecuronium (0.1 mg/kg). Mechanical ventilation was started after intubation of the trachea anesthesia was maintained with Oxygen+N₂O+Isoflurane. Ventilation was controlled with a tidal volume of 6 to 8 mL/kg, Residual neuromuscular block was antagonized with 0.05mg/kg of Inj. neostigmine and 0.01mg/kg glycopyrrolate at the end of surgery. Intra operatively, the adequacy of the block in group SSA, hemodynamic changes, and other complications, such as the occurrence of paresthesia, nausea, vomiting, and pruritus were recorded as well as the duration of the surgery. All patients were transferred to the postoperative room. Postoperative pain was assessed at relaxed conditions by using the visual analog scale (VAS) at the completion of surgery, 4, 8 & 12 hours after the completion of the procedure. Data was described in terms of range, mean ± standard deviation, frequencies (number of cases) and relative frequencies (percentages) as appropriate. Appropriate statistical tests were used & data analyzed using SSPS software. P value <0.05 was considered statistically significant.

III. RESULTS

30 patients were recruited in this study. The mean duration of surgery (mins) in Group SSA is 117.9 compared to that of Group GA which is 119 which shows no significant difference. The mean time requirement for onset of pain postoperatively when VAS ≥3 was significantly longer in patient receiving General anesthesia (GA) as compared with those receiving Segmental spinal anesthesia (SSA) along with ESPB. 4 hours after completion of surgery Group SSA showed mean ± SD of 1.2 ± 0.86 as compared to group GA 2.93 ± 0.70 and p-value <0.001. 8 hours after completion of surgery Group SSA showed mean ± SD of 1.2 ± 0.67 as compared to group GA 2.47 ± 0.64 and p-value <0.001. Both groups were comparable with regards to demographic profile and duration of surgery. Hypotension and bradycardia were reported in 13.3% and 20% respectively of patients in group SSA, whereas hypertension and tachycardia with 26.7% and 33.3% respectively in groups GA. Nausea in 6 patients (40%) and vomiting in 7 patients (46.7%) in group GA were seen as compared to 2 (13.3%) patients each with complaints of nausea and vomiting in group SSA which showed significant difference. Urine retention was seen in 7 (46.7%) patients in group GA.

TABLE 1

Comparison of parameters under study

Demographic Data	Group SSA (n=15)	Group GA (n=15)
Age (Years)	49.6±8.34	50.6±5.65
Weight (KG)	71±8.80	62.2±8.17
Height (cms)	154.4±4.70	150.7±6.2
Physical Status		
ASA I	3	7
ASA II	8	6
ASA III	4	2

TABLE 2

Comparison of intraoperative complications in both groups

<u>Intraoperative Complications</u>	SSA (n=15) (%)	GA (n=15) (%)	Test	P value
Duration of surgery (mean± SD)	117.93 ± 6.123	119 ± 5.82	Mann Whitney U Test = 0.585	0.567
Hypertension	0 (0%)	4 (26.7%)	Fisher's Exact test	0.100
Hypotension	2 (13.3%)	0 (0%)	Fisher's Exact test	0.483
Tachycardia	0 (0%)	5 (33.3%)	Fisher's Exact test	0.042
Bradycardia	3 (20.0%)	0 (0%)	Fisher's Exact test	0.224
Paresthesia	2 (13.3%)	0 (0%)	Fisher's Exact test	0.483

TABLE 3

<u>Intraoperative Complications</u>	SSA	GA	Test	P value
Stay in the recovery room (Minutes)	121.20 ± 8.27 (mean ± SD)	211.33 ± 24.75 (mean ± SD)	Mann Whitney U Test = 4.684	< 0.001*
Nausea	2 (13.3%)	6 (40.0%)	Fisher's Exact test	0.215
Vomiting	2 (13.3%)	7 (46.7%)	Fisher's Exact test	0.109
Urine retention	1 (6.6%)	7 (46.7%)	Fisher's Exact test	0.006*
VAS (mean ± SD) Completion of Surgery	1.13 ± 0.516	3.13 ± 0.915	Mann Whitney U Test = 4.584	< 0.001*
VAS (mean ± SD) 4 hours postoperatively	1.20 ± 0.862	2.93 ± 0.704	Mann Whitney U Test = 4.128	< 0.001*
VAS (mean ± SD) 8 hours postoperatively	1.20 ± 0.676	2.47 ± 0.64	Mann Whitney U Test = 3.990	< 0.001*
VAS (mean ± SD) 12 hours Postoperatively	1.60 ± 0.737	2.33 ± 0.488	Mann Whitney U Test = 2.832	0.011*

TABLE 4

<u>Variables</u>	Group SSA(n=15)	Group GA(n=15)
Surgeon satisfied	14	14
Surgeon Unsatisfied	1	1
Single attempt	13	-
Double attempt	2	-
Patient satisfaction:		
Very satisfied	12	11
Average satisfied	2	2
Dissatisfied	1	2

IV. DISSCUSION

Neuraxial anaesthesia can inhibit the neuroendocrine stress response, and patients who receive regional analgesia have lower opioid requirements. Paravertebral analgesia can reduce opioid requirements after breast surgery. Opioids may themselves inhibit cell-mediated immunity and host anti-tumour defences. Because it negatively affects patients' daily lives, methods to prevent and reduce chronic pain and its severity should be developed. In our study, the segmental thoracic spinal along with ESPB showed some advantages over general anaesthesia for the induction of breast cancer. There were no recorded neurological complications. The amount of CSF at thoracic levels is diminished compared to lumbar and cervical levels, and the thoracic nerve roots are very slight compared to segments above and below. Thus, there is less anaesthetic dilution per segmental unit of distance from the site of injection, and the roots are easily blocked due to their small size, both factors predicting efficient blockade of these segments. The thoracic spinal block was practiced at the mid-thoracic level without any great difficulty. Two patients experienced some paraesthesia during initial insertion of the spinal needle; these symptoms responded to needle withdrawal and not leading to any postoperative sequelae or neurological deficits. Paraesthesia can occur with any technique of spinal anaesthesia, but are of potentially greater significance when the needle is inserted above the termination of the spinal cord. The low potential for cord damage with this technique is also seen. Van Zundert et al. published a case-report in which a patient with severely abnormal respiratory function (chronic obstructive pulmonary disease with severe emphysema attributed to homozygote α -1-anti-trypsin deficiency), requiring continuous oxygen therapy, had frequent respiratory infections and severe functional impairment. Even with minimal activity, the patient developed hypoxemia. Using the thoracic CSE technique, with a minute dose of local anaesthetic, cholecystectomy could be performed successfully, with no problems preoperatively. The patient was discharged from the hospital on day 4 with no further deterioration of his pulmonary function.... Patients undergoing breast surgery are normally associated with a high incidence of postoperative nausea and vomiting (PONV). Troublesome pain and PONV can prolong recovery and hospitalization, and are some of the most common causes of hospital admission following ambulatory surgery. Regional block has a lower incidence of nausea and vomiting, when compared with general anaesthesia, which has been demonstrated in several procedures and studies. In our study, we reported an incidence of 40-50% of PONV among patients of general anaesthesia, compared with significantly lower incidence of 13% in segmental thoracic anaesthesia group. These results are consistent with those of Bansal et al., who mentioned that the incidence of PONV during the 24-hour interval after breast cancer surgery was higher in general anaesthesia group, and that 75% of patients in that group required antiemetic. Postoperative pain varied significantly between groups; in group SSA patients did not complain of very strong or strong pain and the request for supplementary analgesic was lower. Tramadol was not used postoperatively in patients in the spinal group. Adequate control of pain in this situation is important since it makes for a better postoperative period and early hospital discharge, and can have a long-term effect, decreasing complications such as chronic pain. The length of stay in the recovery room and in the hospital was less in the thoracic spinal group compared with the general anaesthesia one. The ability of thoracic spinal anaesthesia to preserve the motor power in both lower limbs. Satisfaction with the anaesthesia was similar in both groups.

V. CONCLUSION

To conclude, thoracic spinal block along with ESPB associated with local anaesthetic and opioid was an adequate option for mastectomy. Among its advantages are the quality of postoperative analgesia, lower incidence of nausea and vomiting, and shorter recovery time, with the consequent early hospital discharge. It can be used successfully and safely for breast surgeries by experienced anesthesiologists with patient and surgeon satisfaction. Cardio-respiratory stability is maintained, though there are remote chances of hypotension or bradycardia as is common with any spinal anaesthesia.

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